

Eastern European Steppe Database

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Abstract

The Eastern European Steppe Database (GIVD ID EU-00-030) includes 6961 vegetation plots of dry grassland vegetation from Eastern Europe (Steppe and Forest-Steppe zones, mountain regions), mainly from Ukraine (4579 relevés), Russia (2403 relevés) and Moldova (203 relevés). 3912 vegetation plots are from different literature sources (66 sources), 219 are from the phytosociological card-index of the M.G. Kholodny Institute of Botany, NAS of Ukraine, 2830 relevés are authors' relevés. They were established in 1935–2019 years. The database comprises mainly the vegetation of the class *Festuco-Brometea* (around 95% of the dataset), and a small proportion of *Koelerio-Corynephoretea canescentis*, *Artemisietea vulgaris*, *Crataego-Prunetea*. The taxonomy of vascular species is given according to Cherepanov (1995) for vascular plants, Ignatov and Afonina (1992) for bryophytes and identification guides of the USSR (1971–1978) and Russia (1996, 1998) for lichens. The database is part of the European Vegetation Archive.

Keywords

Dry grassland, Eastern Europe, forest-steppe zone, steppe, steppe zone

GIVD Fact Sheet

GIVD Database ID: EU-00-030		Last update: 2020-11-09	
Eastern European Steppe Database		Web address:	
Database manager(s): Denys Vynokurov (denys.vynokurov@gmail.com)			
Owner: Denys Vynokurov			
Scope: The database includes the relevés of different types of grasslands from Ukraine. Criteria for inclusion: plot size from 1 to 100 m2 and clear geographic location			
Abstract: The Eastern European Steppe Database (GIVD ID EU-00-030) includes 6961 vegetation plots of dry grassland vegetation from Eastern Europe (Steppe and Forest-Steppe zones, mountain regions), mainly from Ukraine (4579 relevés), Russia (2403 relevés) and Moldova (203 relevés). 3912 vegetation plots are from different literature sources (66 sources), 219 are from the phytosociological card-index of the M.G. Kholodny Institute of Botany, NAS of Ukraine, 2830 relevés are authors' relevés. They were established in 1935-2019 years. The database comprises mainly the vegetation of the class Festuco-Brometea (around 95% of the dataset), and a small proportion of Koelerio-Coryneporetea canescens, Artemisietea vulgaris, Crataego-Prunetea. The taxonomy of vascular species is given according to Cherepanov vascular plants checklist (1995), bryophytes – M. Ignatov & O. Afonina checklist (1992) and lichens – identification guides of the USSR (1971–1978) and Russia (1996, 1998).			
Availability: free upon request		Online upload: no	Online search: no
Database format(s): TURBOVEG		Export format(s): TURBOVEG, Excel	
Plot type(s): normal plots		Plot-size range: 4 to 625	
Non-overlapping plots: 6961	Estimate of existing plots: 6961	Completeness: 100%	Status: completed and continuing
Total no. of plot observations: 6961	Number of sources (biblioreferences, data collectors): 66	Valid taxa: 0	
Countries (%): UA: 62.5; RU: 34.1; MD: 2.9			
Formations: Non Forest: 100% = Terrestrial: 100% (Non arctic-alpin: 100% [Natural: 43%; Semi-natural: 57%])			
Guilds: all vascular plants: 95%; bryophytes (terricolous or aquatic): 1%; lichens (terricolous or aquatic): 1%			
Environmental data (%): altitude: 23; slope aspect: 49; slope inclination: 46; microrelief: 0; surface cover other than plants (open soil, litter, bare rock etc.): 0; other soil attributes: 0; soil pH: 0; land use categories: 0; soil depth: 0			
Performance measure(s): presence/absence only: 0%; cover: 100%; number of individuals: 0%; measurements like diameter or height of trees: 0%; biomass: 0%; other: 0%			
Geographic localisation: GPS coordinates (precision 25 m or less): 20%; point coordinates less precise than GPS, up to 1 km: 75%; small grid (not coarser than 10 km): 0%; political units or only on a coarser scale (above 10 km): 5%			
Sampling periods: before 1920: 0%; 1920-1929: 0%; 1930-1939: 0.07%; 1940-1949: 0.01%; 1950-1959: 0.04%; 1960-1969: 0.3%; 1970-1979: 4.48%; 1980-1989: 6.51%; 1990-1999: 2.33%; 2000-2009: 22.07%; 2010-2019: 28.65%; unknown: 35.54%			
<i>Information as of 2020-12-14 further details and future updates available from http://www.givd.info/ID/EU-00-030</i>			

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